

ENER GIZE

SUPPORTING THE CLEAN ENERGY
TRANSITION OF EUROPEAN BUSINESSES

Communication, Dissemination and Engagement plan

ENERGIZE

SUPPORTING THE CLEAN ENERGY
TRANSITION OF EUROPEAN BUSINESSES

D6.1 – Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Plan

Authors:

Claudia BRIONGOS, Segis VERDAGUER, Olga BARRACHINA (ESTRATS)

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Authors	Claudia BRIONGOS (ESTRATS), Segis VERDAGUER (ESTRATS)
Contributors	Diana BOSFY (FEDARENE), Olga BARRACHINA (ESTRATS), Marta CHÀFER (ICAEN), Anna ARIAS (IRIS)

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Executive Summary

The ENERGIZE project is co-funded by the European Commission through the LIFE Clean Energy Transition program. ENERGIZE aims to demonstrate the potential of cooperative energy models in industrial zones across the EU. These initiatives face considerable challenges - especially in governance, legal frameworks and financial sustainability which ENERGIZE aims to overcome. It will promote energy collaboration through active engagement, capacity building, and the creation of a dedicated digital hub to serve as a support tool. This approach will foster renewable energy projects, resource efficiency, and circularity within these communities.

This document is the second release of the ENERGIZE's Communication, Dissemination and Engagement plan, which updates the communication, dissemination and engagement strategy already fixed in the 1st version of the document, and the corresponding activities to spread the knowledge generated during ENERGIZE project and engage with key stakeholders.

Further updates will be provided as the project progresses.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

ABBREVIATION OR ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
CA	Consortium Agreement
CDEP	Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Plan
EC	Energy Communities
ESCO	Energy Services Companies
ET	Energy Transition
GA	Grant Agreement
IEC	Industrial Energy Communities
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LIFE CET	LIFE Clean Energy Transition
PA	Public Authority
PPs	Project partners
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
TG	Target Groups
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

The Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Plan (CDEP) is part of the activities of Work Package 6, in particular of “*Task 6.1 – Communication and Dissemination of ENERGIZE Project*”, which centralizes most of the coordination and implementation of the project’s communication and dissemination activities. Task 6.1 consists of different subtasks:

- T6.1.1: Communication, dissemination and engagement plan and coordination
- T6.1.2: Communication material and tools, which includes:
 - Project brand and visual identity
 - Landing webpage and blog
 - Project brochure
 - Communication videos
- T6.1.3: Dissemination activities and communication campaigns, which includes:
 - Social media
 - Press releases and newsletter
 - Communication campaigns
 - Site visits
 - Participation in public events
 - Networking with other LIFE projects
 - Final ENERGIZE International Workshop

The CDEP will constitute the core document outlining the activities at the basis of the project’s dissemination and communication activities, and will set up and manage an effective communication and dissemination strategy to guarantee the professional and public coverage of the project results, and to maximise the visibility of the project results and actions to all the stakeholders and target audience.

It will be subject to revision every 12 months in order to fine tune the dissemination, communication and engagement objectives with project results, and include potential new communication tools and targets that may appear over time. Thus, this 2nd CDEP will aim at selecting which results should be given priority and how they need to be communicated within the second year of the project.

Complementarily to this CDEP, the ENERGIZE project has foreseen the development of a Stakeholder Engagement Strategy (D5.1, by month 12), which complements the activities planned within this deliverable.

2 Communication and Dissemination Strategy

2.1 Overall objectives

All communication and dissemination activities have been designed to impact the specific segmented target audience of the project. The main objectives of communication, dissemination and engagement activities are:

- Reducing the knowledge gap for the actors involved.
- Facilitating and easing the establishment of industrial energy communities and clusters.
- Supporting optimal conditions and solutions for the replication and exploitation of the project outcomes.
- Consolidating the project visibility among the industry sector and stakeholders at EU level to enhance awareness.
- Guaranteeing the scientific and public coverage of the project results.

These objectives are closely aligned with the [LIFE Programme Communication rules](#), which highlights the need to communicate the benefits of EU funded projects to the whole society.

2.2 Key principles

The communication activities will be grouped and planned at four levels, according to their communication objectives:

Pilot territories level

This level focuses on communication and marketing to ensure the deployment of the ENERGIZE project within pilot regions. It aims to engage stakeholders and raise awareness among industries and public authorities. The communication strategy will consist of communicating information about the specific pilot case, its milestones, progress and news. The project website, social media and local press will be the key communication channels. Local language will be prioritized.

Supra-regional and national level

Communication and marketing to ensure the scale-up of ENERGIZE pilots to the whole region/country, depending on the pilot case, and inform stakeholders, other industries, public authorities (local, regional and national) and general public. The communication will be focused on explaining the project and its potential scale-up to neighbour regions around pilot cases, including project progress and news. The project website and social media will be the key communication channels. Local language and English will be used.

Replication at a wide EU level

At this level, broader communication, to all EU stakeholders, to maximize the replication of ENERGIZE methodologies and the expansion at EU level of the ENERGIZE Digital Hub (the “One-Stop-Shop” interface for accessing project outputs and for hosting a pan-European virtual stakeholder community linked to energy cooperation). The communication will explain the project's contributions to energy transition (ET) and highlight achievements from the pilot territories. This will encourage industries, clusters, and regions across the EU to participate in the replication phase and adopt some of the project results. The website and social media will be the key communication channels. English language will be prioritized.

Mainstream level

This levels aims to communicate project objectives, progress and results with a wider audience and various target groups throughout the EU. This communication level includes all general communication activities and channels.

Figure 2-1 – Principle schema of communication and dissemination activities

3 Target audience

The target audience of ENERGIZE communication, dissemination and engagement activities includes all the key stakeholders identified as potential contributors to enhance the achievement of the project's goals in terms of cooperative energy model capacity building, implementation and replicability.

Each of these stakeholders plays a crucial role in facilitating energy cooperation and collaborative approaches in various contexts, from value chains to local communities and industrial parks. They have the potential to make valuable contributions in terms of providing specialized knowledge, offering access to relevant networks or resources, and participating in co-creation and collaborative activities that align with the project's mission, among other contributions.

3.1 Priority Target Groups

The overall success of the **ENERGIZE+** project fundamentally relies on the expertise and efforts of the consortium members, as well as the engagement and participation of the target groups, both within the project pilots and beyond.

The identification of target groups takes into account the importance of the different key actors for the successful development of the project. In this regard, the most relevant and priority target groups for ENERGIZE project are:

Table 3-1 – Priority Target Groups of ENERGIZE Communication and Dissemination strategy

TG	Target Group	Importance
TG1	Local and regional industrial parks and clusters	They play a central role in energy cooperation and can provide valuable insights into local energy needs and potential collaboration opportunities.
TG2	Industry associations and chambers of commerce	They represent the interests of businesses within specific sectors and can facilitate broader industry adoption of clean energy practices.
TG3	Energy agencies, public authorities (e.g. focused on energy policies)	They set and hold expertise in the policies and regulatory frameworks that can hinder or support clean energy initiatives, and can provide valuable data and insights for project analysis.
TG4	Financial institutions, aggregators, investors	They play a crucial role in securing funding for energy efficiency and renewable energy projects, providing necessary capital for successful launch and rollout of energy communities.

Furthermore, ENERGIZE will also target any potential contributor to enhance the achievement of the project's goals in terms of cooperative energy model capacity building, set up and replicability, such as:

Table 3-2 – Other relevant Target Groups (2nd level) of ENERGIZE Communication and Dissemination strategy

TG	Target Group	Importance
TG5	Energy Services stakeholders: ESCOs, energy consultants, utility companies, RES providers & installers, HVAC providers & installers	They specialise in renewable and/or energy efficiency solutions, offering valuable expertise in project implementation.
TG6	Local communities, residents, general public	Their buy-in and support are critical for the successful deployment of energy communities.

3.2 Tailored strategy to Target Groups

The communication, dissemination and engagement activities will be tailored to the different target groups, to maximise the efficiency of the action. In particular, the key message and specific channels for the different audiences include:

Table 3-3 – Specific target audience communication, dissemination and engagement messages and channels

TG	Key objectives, specific channels
TG1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Obj: Highlight the benefits of participating in the project, such as reduced operating costs, improved sustainability, new tailored services.
TG2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Obj: Conduct targeted outreach and workshops to foster engagement. Obj: Showcase the State-of-the-Art analysis of energy cooperation landscape, to promote synergies and collaboration between different organisations and entities. Key channels: workshops, webinars, LinkedIn
TG3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Obj: Highlight benefits of fostering and replicating the project for the territory, such as enhancement of Energy Transition and reduction of emissions. To engage in dialogue to ensure alignment of project activities with regional energy policies. Obj: Showcase the State-of-the-Art analysis of energy cooperation landscape, to promote synergies and collaboration between different organisations and entities. Key channels: workshops, webinars, LinkedIn, X
TG4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Obj: Showcase new business models and services, opportunities for financial operators. Promote partnerships to explore funding options and new business models. Key channels: workshops, LinkedIn
TG5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Obj: Showcase new business models and services, new opportunities for promotion of RES. Promote the development of new energy efficiency measures. Obj: Showcase the State-of-the-Art analysis of energy cooperation landscape, to promote synergies and collaboration between different organisations and entities. Key channels: webinars, LinkedIn, X, Instagram

TG6

- Obj: Awareness raising on Energy Transition and energy communities.
- Key channels: LinkedIn, X, Instagram

4 Communication, dissemination and engagement channels

4.1 Promotional material

The promotional materials consist of:

- A general roll up banner in English, to present the project in any stand or side event.
- A detailed roll up in English, including details on the objectives, pilots and expected impact.
- A project flyer -postcard format- printed in the five project languages, describing the project objectives, the proposed methodology and the expected results.
- A project brochure in English, highlighting the project approach and key project achievements.

4.2 Project website

As a key channel for interaction with the engaged stakeholders of the project and the selected target groups, a project website will be created. It will be the key tool to communicate and disseminate information about the progress and the results achieved by the project. The website will include a repository of information, considered as a lively tool with continuously updated content (news and press releases, original articles and interviews, posts of project-related news from external sources, cross-linking).

The website will be available in English and the national languages of pilots (German, Italian, Czech and Catalan). In addition, each project partner will create a special section on its own website in its national language, describing briefly the project and dedicated to the promotion of its results.

In addition to the project landing page, project partners (PPs) will need to present the project in their own websites or social media accounts. This should include, at least:

- Project summary.
- Project logo.
- List of participants.
- Contact details
- European flag and funding statement
- Project results (when available)

4.3 Project videos

Communication videos will be a key way to raise awareness on the positive impact of energy communities on the framework of ENERGIZE project. These videos aim to raise awareness and encourage public authorities to adopt the project's outcomes.

Several videos will be created, in close cooperation with pilot partners, in particular:

- 1 constitutional video (2 minutes length) explaining the project approach and expected impacts, to be produced at M8.
- 1 replicability video (2 minutes length) addressing project results and key outcomes, to be produced at M30.
- 10 short video clips (15" length) sharing engaging content (e.g. infographics, factsheets and testimonials) to foster adoption of project solutions.

4.4 Social media accounts

Social media represents another essential channel for mainstream communication as well as specific target audience engagement. Specific ENERGIZE profiles have been developed in different channels.

ESTRATS is the main responsible for managing the project's social media accounts but all ENERGIZE partners are encouraged to widen the coverage of the project through their own social media channels. Their support is of high importance to inform ESTRATS about events and developments on one hand, and to increase the audience by promoting and participating in the different social networks on the other hand.

The key parameters of the ENERGIZE project's social media strategy are:

- Proactive Content Planning: Planning the communication content at least 21 days in advance, so providing a communication calendar.
- Consistent Publishing Schedule: Publishing at least twice a week is expected.
- Personalized and Impactful Messaging: Writing in a more personal way and using impactful messages to better engage the general public.
- High-Quality Visual Content: Using interesting and good quality pictures to ensure content is suitable for different channels.

4.4.1 LinkedIn

LinkedIn is the most used platform among ENERGIZE target groups, therefore it is one of the most relevant tools for the communication, dissemination and engagement strategy. It will be used to target almost all the target groups (TG1 to TG5). Regular publications will be published, around 4-8 per month on average, with short information about the project activities or outcomes. During the second half of the project, longer articles to highlight specific project results will be published regularly.

LinkedIn handle: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/energizcommunity>

4.4.2 X (formerly Twitter)

Public authorities and individuals are still very present in this social media channel, so ENERGIZE will use it as a relevant communication channel with TG3 as well as TG5 and TG6. Furthermore, it can be very useful for clustering and networking with other EU projects.

X handle: <https://x.com/energizecom>

4.4.3 Instagram

The audience reached by Instagram focuses more on the general public (TG6), but also on providers and installers of HVAC, RES, etc (TG5). ENERGIZE will feed this channel with very visual posts, with catchy images and/or videos, as well as stories for specific occasions (e.g. project meetings, and specific achievements).

Instagram handle: <https://www.instagram.com/energizcommunity/>

4.4.4 YouTube

YouTube will be a very important communication tool for ENERGIZE. It will work as a visual repository of the videos generated by the project, including not only the ENERGIZE produced videos (see section 4.3) but also those public webinars and workshop that have been recorded, so that everybody has access to them if they missed the date where the webinar or workshop took place.

Youtube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/@EnergizcommunityLIFE>

4.4.5 Share with official LIFE channels

ENERGIZE will also share news and stories about project with the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) through their own social media channels, in particular:

- [LinkedIn](#): @LIFEprogramme
- [Twitter](#): @LIFEprogramme
- [Instagram](#): @LIFEprogramme

Furthermore, all publications related to the project should consider these LIFE main hashtags:

Table 4-1 – LIFE main hashtags

General	Climate and Energy
#LIFEprogramme #LIFEproject #LIFEprojects	#EnergyTransition #CleanEnergyEU #ClimateNeutralEU #EU2050

Finally, highly relevant communication material (such as press releases, videos, or high relevant news) will be shared with CINEA communication team by email (CINEA-COMMUNICATION-LIFE@ec.europa.eu) to enhance its visibility.

4.5 Press releases and newsletters

Good press coverage is essential to increase the long-term visibility and impact of the project.

A total of at least six press releases will be produced and distributed throughout the project, particularly when milestones or high interest outcomes are reached. They will be written in English, and distributed

to a wide EU audience through the website, social media channels, EU-wide multipliers such as Build Up platform or similar. They will also be submitted to the LIFE+ Communication Team for potential dissemination through LIFE channels.

ENERGIZE will also publish a total of 6 newsletters in English, every 6 months. Each one will include the most relevant news from the previous period, as well as any update from PPs. These newsletters will be distributed to web registered users, and will also be available through the project website and LinkedIn channel. Furthermore, PPs will be encouraged to include the newsletters in their own communications to maximize reach.

4.6 Communication campaigns

ENERGIZE will design and implement three specific awareness raising campaigns to promote the engagement of private stakeholders and interaction with Energy Agencies, Local and Regional Authorities and citizens.

The preliminary aim of the 3 communication campaigns has been already done, including expected planning, which has been updated for the 1st one, according to the expected project results.

Table 4-2 – Details of the Communication Campaigns

#	Objective	Expected planning
#1	To highlight the key specifications for setting up a successful urban industrial energy community. Related to milestone M4	M15
#2	To foster user registration, after the launch of the 1 st version of the Energy Hub. Related to milestone M7.	M20
#3	To foster user registration and engagement to the Energy Hub once all the training material and KPIs dashboard have been integrated in the Energy Hub. Related to milestone M9	M30

The proposed planning and content could be adapted to the necessities and progress of the project.

4.7 Site visits

Project partners will organise at least 3 site visits, that will be conceived as learning expeditions to showcase best practices in project regions, in particular in Manresa region, Valsesia region and Linz region. The main learnings from these site visits will be documented in engaging formats for dissemination. The specific content of the site visits will be planned together with the pilots regions.

4.8 Public events and clustering

4.8.1 Participation in public events and conferences

ENERGIZE+ will be presented in at least 10 national or international conferences, strategic workshops, seminars, fairs, or workshops relevant to industrial energy cooperatives. The aim is to share project outcomes, enlarge the dissemination reach of the project and promote the growth of the community in the ENERGIZE digital hub.

In particular, it is expected to present the project in two conferences per pilot country (Austria, Italy, Czech Republic, Catalonia) and two additional events in other EU regions. However, this planning will be adapted following the needs and requirements of the project development.

4.8.2 Clustering with sister projects

Networking with other LIFE projects is also essential for increasing the reach and visibility of the project. ENERGIZE will promote clustering with at least 6 other relevant projects, to leverage synergies and foster cooperation.

4.8.3 Final ENERGIZE International Workshop

Towards the end of the project, ENERGIZE will organize an international workshop to present the final project results and showcase case studies, methodologies, guidelines, best practices, and business models.

To maximize impact, this event could be planned to coincide with a synergistic conference or exhibition for high impact, such as the European Sustainable Energy Week (EUSEW), the World Sustainable Energy Days (WSED), or any other similar event. Expected audience: 50 attendees.

4.9 Final publishable report

ENERGIZE will prepare a final publishable report presenting the key results, main lessons learnt, and recommendations for the future. The final publication should be professionally designed, attractive and tailored to the target group. The content and final draft of the publishable report must be discussed with CINEA before publication.

5 Monitoring

5.1 What to monitor

It is essential to understand the audience that has been reached by the project, both in quantitative and qualitative parameters. The reactions generated by the project and the level of satisfaction of the audience are curial to better focus the following communication actions.

Monitoring activities will follow next scheme:

Figure 5-1 – Principles of monitoring and evaluation

5.2 Communication and dissemination KPIs

Next tables include the means of evaluation of the different communication and dissemination activities. The related KPIs are the objectives at the end of the project (M36) as well as the real values monitored up to the 20. June. 2025. All the indicators are on track, considering the expected planning of the activities.

Table 5-1 – Communication and dissemination activities KPIs

COMMUNICATION AREA	KPIs	M36	M12
PROJECT WEBSITE	Number of unique visitors Number of page views	2000+ 7500+	2000+ 7500+
SOCIAL MEDIA	Number of followers Average publications per month	+50/quarter 15	219 11
VIDEOS	Number of short videos Number of views / reach of short videos	10 200+	4 266

	Number of long videos	2	1
	Number of views / reach of long videos	400+	--
NEWSLETTER	Number of publications	6	1
	Number of reach / impressions / interactions	200+	90
PRESS RELEASES	Number of publications	6	--
AWARENESS RAISING CAMPAIGNS	Number of awareness raising campaigns	3	--
	Number of reach / impressions / interactions	3000+	--
CONFERENCES & EVENTS	Number of participated events	10	2
	Number of events organised by the project	1	--
	Number of attendants in organised events	50	--
SITE VISITS	Number of site visits	3	1
	Number of attendees	60+	20
CLUSTERING	Number of similar projects approached	6	2
ENERGIZE DIGITAL HUB	Number of registered users	200+	--
ENERGIZE NETWORK	Number of registered professional members to the project subscription list	200+	--

6 Dissemination of results & open access

6.1 Obligation to disseminate results

Dissemination (Grant Agreement – article 17) is a separate obligation. In that sense, each beneficiary must “disseminate” its results as soon as possible by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means, unless it goes against their legitimate interests. This does not change the obligation to protect results, confidentiality obligations, security obligations, or the obligation to protect personal data.

6.2 Information on EU funding – Obligation and right to use the LIFE emblem

Any communication activities (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant **must include**:

- a) The LIFE Programme flag. High resolution emblems can be found here:
https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/programmes/life/communication-and-gdpr-rules_en
- b) The following statement:
Co-funded by the European Union, under Grant Agreement N° 101167570.

6.3 Disclaimer excluding EU responsibility

Whenever using the funding logo (LIFE programme flag, EU logo, etc), this disclaimer will be used:

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7 Specific communication actions during the 2nd year

The updated communication and dissemination plan for the ENERGIZE project outlines a clear and well-structured roadmap for the upcoming year. With all planned actions on track and no foreseeable obstacles, the focus remains on raising awareness, engaging key stakeholders, and promoting the project's outcomes across targeted channels. Moving forward, efforts will concentrate on ensuring consistent visibility, strengthening collaborations, and supporting the uptake of ENERGIZE solutions through strategic communication on both local and international levels.

Table 7-1 – Communication and dissemination activities during 2nd year of the project

ACTION	DEADLINE
Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Plan (update)	M24
Project reference in partners' websites	M15
Update of the "Resources" section of ENERGIZE website and Zenodo repository	M16
4 short videos	M13 - M24
Social Media – continue uploading content	M13 – M24
2 newsletters	M13, M18
3 press releases	M13 - M24
2 communication campaigns	M15, M20
Definition of collaboration framework with first sister projects	M18
Clustering with at least 2 sister projects, contacting at least 2 additional sister projects	M21

8 Annex 1 – Communication & Dissemination activities performed

This section will be updated during the update of the communication and dissemination plan, such as the following activities cover M1-M12 timeline.

M4 – Project website (D6.2)

The project website has been created following planned timeline. It's available at www.energizcommunity.eu.

The ENERGIZE website has been designed to be user-friendly and easy to use, with a smooth transition between the different sections and some transversal functionalities (e.g. social networks, contact form, siubscription to newsletter, news, languages) that are present in different sections.

Figure 8-1 – “Home” and “Resources” sections (partial view), and Google Analytics results

M6 – project flyer (D6.2)

The project flyer has been designed following the proposed timeline.

The flyer has been created in English and the national languages of the four ENERGIZE demo sites.

Figure 8-2 – Pilot region’s versions

M6 – project poster

A specific poster and a project roll-up have been designed for increasing the project visibility at fairs and conferences, or for other project events. The poster provides a clear and simple introduction to the project, showcasing social media channels and involved partners.

Figure 8-3 – ENERGIZE poster

M6 – 1st newsletter released

The first ENERGIZE newsletter has been released by beginning January 2025, with a summary of the most relevant news of the project. The current number of subscriptions to the newsletter being still small, the newsletter has also been directly distributed to the project partners (to include it on their own newsletters) as well as through LinkedIn, X and the project website.

M10 – Constitutional video (D6.4)

The ENERGIZE constitutional video has been produced following the planned timeline. The 72 seconds length video, available at the ENERGIZE Youtube channel, focuses on the project goals and future outcomes to increase the interest of industries and businesss into the project activities.

Figure 8-4 – Frame of the constitutional video

M10 – Short videos

ENERGIZE team has been producing a set of short videos from different activities.

On one hand, the constitutional video has been designed to be divided and presented in 3 different short videos presenting the current situation (phase 1), the challenge (phase 2) and the solution (phase 3). These 20 seconds videos have been already designed, and an ongoing promotion through Social Media channels is being undertaken, in particular LinkedIn, to maximise the project visibility.

Furthermore, several short videos from the partners have been already promoted, highlighting their different roles and points of views regarding the ENERGIZE project.

All these and the forthcoming short videos will be promoted mainly through social media channels, as well as Youtube shorts section.

Figure 8-5 – Frame of the several short videos

M2-M12 – Social media: LinkedIn & Instagram

The ENERGIZE actions include the creation of a LinkedIn “project page”, together with X and Instagram accounts, which centralise all the social media communication activities. More than 200 followers have been activated during the 1st year of the project, considering both platforms. Due to the direction and inconsistent policy taken by X in recent months ENERGIZE partners have agreed to shift their communication regarding ENERGIZE project efforts to LinkedIn and Instagram.

During the 1st year of the project, the communication activities have been mainly focused on information about the project objectives, and general awareness raising on the need to enhance energy cooperatives in industrial areas.

Figure 8-6 – samples of LinkedIn posts

Figure 8-7 – samples of Instagram posts

More information: www.energizcommunity.eu

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ANNEX

The first version of deliverable *D6.1 – Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Plan*, which was submitted in M5, is attached as an annex to the M12 version of the deliverable.

The upcoming updated versions of this deliverable, expected in M24 and M30, will also include all previous versions as annexes.

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Communication, Dissemination and Engagement plan

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D6.1 – Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Plan

Authors:

Claudia BRIONGOS, Segis VERDAGUER, Olga BARRACHINA (ESTRATS)

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Authors	Claudia BRIONGOS (ESTRATS), Segis VERDAGUER (ESTRATS)
Contributors	Diana PRSANCOVA (FEDARENE), Olga BARRACHINA (ESTRATS), Marta CHÀFER (ICAEN)

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Executive Summary

ENERGIZE project is cofounded by the European Commission through the LIFE Clean Energy Transition program. ENERGIZE aims to demonstrate the potential of cooperative energy models in industrial zones across the EU. These initiatives face considerable challenges -especially in governance, legal frameworks and financial sustainability- which ENERGIZE aims to overcome. It will promote energy collaboration through active engagement, capacity building, and the creation of a dedicated digital hub to serve as a support tool. This approach will foster renewable energy projects, resource efficiency, and circularity within these communities.

This document is the 1st version of the ENERGIZE's Communication, Dissemination and Engagement plan, which fixes the communication, dissemination and engagement strategy and the corresponding activities to spread the knowledge generated during ENERGIZE project and engage with key stakeholders.

Further releases will be elaborated during project progress.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

ABBREVIATION OR ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
CA	Consortium Agreement
CDEP	Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Plan
EC	Energy Communities
ESCO	Energy Services Companies
ET	Energy Transition
GA	Grant Agreement
IEC	Industrial Energy Communities
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LIFE CET	LIFE Clean Energy Transition
PA	Public Authority
PPs	Project partners
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
TG	Target Groups
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

The Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Plan (CDEP) is part of the activities of Work Package 6, in particular of “*Task 6.1 – Communication and Dissemination of ENERGIZE Project*”, which centralizes most of the coordination and implementation of project’s communication and dissemination activities. Task 6.1 consists of different subtasks:

- T6.1.1: Communication, dissemination and engagement plan and coordination
- T6.1.2: Communication material and tools, which includes:
 - Project brand and visual identity
 - Landing webpage and blog
 - Project brochure
 - Communication videos
- T6.1.3: Dissemination activities and communication campaigns, which includes:
 - Social media
 - Press releases and newsletter
 - Communication campaigns
 - Site visits
 - Participation in public events
 - Networking with other LIFE projects
 - Final ENERGIZE International Workshop

The CDEP will constitute the core document outlining the activities at the basis of the project’s dissemination and communication activities, and will set up and manage an effective communication and dissemination strategy to guarantee the professional and public coverage of the project results, and to maximise the visibility of the project results and actions to all the stakeholders and target audience.

It will be subject to revision every 12 months in order to fine tune the dissemination, communication and engagement objectives with project results, and include potential new communication tools and targets that may appear over time. Thus, this 1st CDEP will aim at selecting which results should be given priority and how they need to be communicated within the first 12 months of the project.

Complementarily to this CDEP, the ENERGIZE project has foreseen the development of a Stakeholder Engagement Strategy (D5.1, by month 12). Additional engagement activities following that Stakeholders Engagement Strategy will be included in the second version of this deliverable.

2 Communication and Dissemination Strategy

2.1 Overall objectives

All communication and dissemination activities have been designed to impact the specific segmented target audience of the project. The main objectives of communication, dissemination and engagement activities are:

- Reducing the knowledge gap for the actors involved.
- Facilitating and easing the establishment of industrial energy communities and clusters.
- Supporting optimal conditions and solutions for the replication and exploitation of the project outcomes.
- Consolidating the project visibility among the industry sector and stakeholders at EU level to enhance awareness.
- Guaranteeing the scientific and public coverage of the project results.

These objectives are closely related with European “Communication EU research and innovation guidance for project participants” handbook, which highlights the need to communicate the benefits of EU funded projects to the whole society.

2.2 Key principles

The communication activities will be grouped and planned at four levels, according to their communication objectives:

Pilot territories level

This level focuses on communication and marketing to ensure the deployment of the ENERGIZE project within pilot regions. It aims to engage stakeholders and raise awareness among industries and public authorities. The communication strategy will consist in communicating information about the specific pilot case, its milestones, progress and news. The project website, social media and local press will be the key communication channels. Local language will be prioritized.

Supra-regional and national level

Communication and marketing to ensure the scale-up of ENERGIZE pilots to the whole region/country, depending on the pilot case, and inform stakeholders, other industries, public authorities (local, regional and national) and general public. The communication will be focused on explaining the project and its potential scale-up to neighbour regions around pilot cases, including project progress and news. The project website and social media will be the key communication channels. Local language and English will be used.

Replication at a wide EU level

At this level, broader communication, to all EU stakeholders, to maximize the replication of ENERGIZE methodologies and the expansion at EU level of the ENERGIZE Digital Hub (the “One-Stop-Shop” interface for accessing project outputs and for hosting a pan-European virtual stakeholder community linked to energy cooperation). The communication will explain the project's contributions to energy transition (ET) and highlight achievements from the pilot territories. This will encourage industries, clusters, and regions across the EU to participate in the replication phase and adopt some of the project results. The website and social media will be the key communication channels. English language will be prioritized.

Mainstream level

This levels aims to communicate project objectives, progress and results with a wider audience and various target groups throughout the EU. This communication level includes all general communication activities and channels.

Figure 2-1 – Principle schema of communication and dissemination activities

3 Target audience

The target audience of ENERGIZE communication, dissemination and engagement activities includes all the key stakeholders identified as potential contributors to enhance the achievement of the project's goals in terms of cooperative energy model capacity building, implementation and replicability.

Each of these stakeholders plays a crucial role in facilitating energy cooperation and collaborative approaches in various contexts, from value chains to local communities and industrial parks. They have the potential to make valuable contributions in terms of providing specialized knowledge, offering access to relevant networks or resources, and participating in co-creation and collaborative activities that align with the project's mission, among other contributions.

3.1 Priority Target Groups

The overall success of **ENERGIZE+** project fundamentally relies on the expertise and efforts of the consortium members, as well as the engagement and participation of the target groups, both within the project pilots and beyond.

The identification of target groups takes into account the importance of the different key actors for the successful development of the project. In this regard, the most relevant and priority target groups for ENERGIZE project are:

Table 3-1 – Priority Target Groups of ENERGIZE Communication and Dissemination strategy

TG	Target Group	Importance
TG1	Local and regional industrial parks and clusters	They play a central role in energy cooperation and can provide valuable insights into local energy needs and potential collaboration opportunities.
TG2	Industry associations and chambers of commerce	They represent the interests of businesses within specific sectors and can facilitate broader industry adoption of clean energy practices.
TG3	Energy agencies, public authorities (e.g. focused on energy policies)	They set and hold expertise in the policies and regulatory frameworks that can hinder or support clean energy initiatives, and can provide valuable data and insights for project analysis.
TG4	Financial institutions, aggregators, investors	They play a crucial role in securing funding for energy efficiency and renewable energy projects, providing necessary capital for successful launch and rollout of energy communities.

Furthermore, ENERGIZE will also target any potential contributor to enhance the achievement of the project's goals in terms of cooperative energy model capacity building, set up and replicability, such as:

Table 3-2 – Other relevant Target Groups (2nd level) of ENERGIZE Communication and Dissemination strategy

TG	Target Group	Importance
TG5	Energy Services stakeholders: ESCOs, energy consultants, utility companies, RES providers & installers, HVAC providers & installers	They specialise in renewable and/or energy efficiency solutions, offering valuable expertise in project implementation.
TG6	Local communities, residents, general public	Their buy-in and support are critical for the successful deployment of energy communities.

3.2 Tailored strategy to Target Groups

The communication, dissemination and engagement activities will be tailored to the different target groups, to maximise the efficiency of the action. In particular, the key message and specific channels for the different audiences include:

Table 3-3 – Specific target audience communication, dissemination and engagement messages and channels

TG	Key objectives, specific channels
TG1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Objective: Highlight the benefits of participating in the project, such as reduced operating costs, improved sustainability, new tailored services.
TG2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Obj: Conduct targeted outreach and workshops to foster engagement. Obj: Showcase the State-of-the-Art analysis of energy cooperation landscape, to promote synergies and collaboration between different organisations and entities. Key channels: workshops, webinars, LinkedIn
TG3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Obj: Highlight benefits of fostering and replicating the project for the territory, such as enhancement of Energy Transition and reduction of emissions. To engage in dialogue to ensure alignment of project activities with regional energy policies. Obj: Showcase the State-of-the-Art analysis of energy cooperation landscape, to promote synergies and collaboration between different organisations and entities. Key channels: workshops, webinars, LinkedIn, X
TG4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Obj: Showcase new business models and services, opportunities for financial operators. Promote partnerships to explore funding options and new business models. Key channels: workshops, LinkedIn
TG5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Obj: Showcase new business models and services, new opportunities for promotion of RES. Promote the development of new energy efficiency measures. Obj: Showcase the State-of-the-Art analysis of energy cooperation landscape, to promote synergies and collaboration between different organisations and entities. Key channels: webinars, LinkedIn, X, Instagram

TG6

- Obj: Awareness raising on Energy Transition and energy communities.
- Key channels: LinkedIn, X, Instagram

4 Communication, dissemination and engagement channels

4.1 Promotional material

The promotional material will consist of:

- A general roll up in English, to frame the project in any stand or side event.
- A detailed roll up in English, including details on the objectives, pilots and expected impact.
- A project flyer printed in the 5 project languages, describing the project objectives, the proposed methodology and the expected results.
- A project brochure in English, highlighting the project approach and key project achievements.

4.2 Project website

As a key channel for interaction with the engaged stakeholders of the project and the selected target groups, a project website will be created. It will be the key tool to communicate and disseminate information about the progress and the results achieved by the project. The website will include a repository of information, considered as a lively tool with continuously updated content (news and press releases, original articles and interviews, posts of project-related news from external sources, cross-linking).

The website will be available in English and the national languages of pilots (German, Italian, Czech and Catalan). In addition, each project partner will create a special section on its own website in its national language, describing briefly the project and dedicated to the promotion of its results.

Additionally to the project landing page, PPs will need to present the project in their own websites or social media accounts. This should include, at least:

- Project summary.
- Project logo.
- List of participants.
- Contact details
- European flag and funding statement
- Project results (when available)

4.3 Project videos

Communication videos will be a key way to raise awareness on the positive impact of energy communities on the framework of ENERGIZE project. These videos aim to raise awareness and encourage public authorities to adopt the project's outcomes.

Several videos will be created, in close cooperation with pilot partners, in particular:

- 1 constitutional video (2 minutes length) explaining the project approach and expected impacts, to be produced at M8.
- 1 replicability video (2 minutes length) addressing project results and key outcomes, to be produced at M30.
- 10 short video clips (15" length) sharing engaging content (e.g. infographics, factsheets and testimonials) to foster adoption of project solutions.

4.4 Social media accounts

Social media represents another essential channel for mainstream communication as well as specific target audience engagement. Specific ENERGIZE profiles have been developed in different channels.

ESTRATS is the main responsible for managing the project's social media accounts but all ENERGIZE partners are encouraged to widen the coverage of the project through their own social media channels. Their support is of high importance to inform ESTRATS about events and developments on one hand, and to increase the audience by promoting and participating in the different social networks on the other hand.

The key parameters of the social media strategy of ENERGIZE project consists on:

- Proactive Content Planning: Planning the communication content at least 21 days in advance, so providing a communication calendar.
- Consistent Publishing Schedule: Expecting to publish at least twice a week.
- Personalized and Impactful Messaging: Writing in a more personal way and using impacting messages to get closer to the general public.
- High-Quality Visual Content: Using interesting and good quality pictures to be able to use the same content at the different channels.

4.4.1 LinkedIn

LinkedIn is the most used platform among ENERGIZE target groups, therefore it is one of the most relevant tools for the communication, dissemination and engagement strategy. It will be used to target almost all the target groups (TG1 to TG5). Regular publications will be published, around 4-8 per month on average, with short information about the project activities or outcomes. During the second half of the project, longer articles to highlight specific project results will be published regularly.

LinkedIn handle: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/energizcommunity>

4.4.2 X (formerly Twitter)

Public authorities and individuals are still very present in this social media channel, so ENERGIZE will use it as a relevant communication channel with TG3 as well as TG5 and TG6. Furthermore, it can be very useful for clustering and networking with other EU projects.

X handle: <https://x.com/energizecom>

4.4.3 Instagram

The audience reached by Instagram focuses more on the general public (TG6), but also on providers and installers of HVAC, RES, etc (TG5). ENERGIZE will feed this channel with very visual posts, with catchy images and/or videos, as well as stories for specific occasions (e.g. project meetings, and specific achievements).

Instagram handle: <https://www.instagram.com/energizcommunity/>

4.4.4 YouTube

YouTube will be a very important communication tool for ENERGIZE. It will work as a visual repository of the videos generated by the project, including not only the ENERGIZE produced videos (see section 4.3) but also those public webinars and workshop that have been recorded, so that everybody has access to them if they missed the date where the webinar or workshop took place.

Youtube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/@EnergizcommunityLIFE>

4.4.5 Share with official LIFE channels

ENERGIZE will also share news and stories about project with the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) through their own social media channels, in particular:

- [LinkedIn](#) : @LIFEprogramme
- [Twitter](#): @LIFEprogramme
- [Instagram](#): @LIFEprogramme

Furthermore, all publications related to the project should consider these LIFE main hashtags:

Table 4-1 – LIFE main hashtags

General	Climate and Energy
#LIFEprogramme #LIFEproject #LIFEprojects	#EnergyTransition #CleanEnergyEU #ClimateNeutralEU #EU2050

Finally, highly relevant communication material (such as press releases, videos, or high relevant news) will be shared with CINEA communication team by email (CINEA-COMMUNICATION-LIFE@ec.europa.eu) to enhance its visibility.

4.5 Press releases and newsletters

Good press coverage is essential to increase the long-term visibility and impact of the project.

A total of at least 6 press releases will be produced and distributed throughout the project, particularly when milestones or high interest outcomes are reached. They will be written in English, and distributed

to a wide EU audience through the website, social media channels, EU-wide multipliers such as Build Up platform or similar. They will also be submitted to the LIFE+ Communication Team for potential dissemination through LIFE channels.

ENERGIZE will also publish a total of 6 newsletters in English, every 6 months. Each one will include the most relevant news from the previous period, as well as any update from PPs. These newsletters will be distributed to web registered users, and will also be available through the project website and LinkedIn channel. Furthermore, PPs will be encouraged to include the newsletters in their own communications to maximize reach.

4.6 Communication campaigns

ENERGIZE will design and implement three specific awareness raising campaigns to promote the engagement of private stakeholders and interaction with Energy Agencies, Local and Regional Authorities and citizens.

The preliminary aim of the 3 communication campaigns has been already done, including expected planning.

Table 4-2 – Details of the Communication Campaigns

#	Objective	Expected planning
#1	To highlight the key specifications for setting up a successful urban industrial energy community. Related to milestone M4	M10
#2	To foster user registration, after the launch of the 1 st version of the Energy Hub. Related to milestone M7.	M20
#3	To foster user registration and engagement to the Energy Hub once all the training material and KPIs dashboard have been integrated in the Energy Hub. Related to milestone M9	M30

The proposed planning and content could be adapted to the necessities and progress of the project.

4.7 Site visits

Project partners will organise at least 3 site visits, that will be conceived as learning expeditions to showcase best practices in project regions, in particular in Manresa region, Valsesia region and Linz region. The main learnings from these site visits will be documented in engaging formats for dissemination. The specific content of the site visits will be planned together with the pilots regions.

4.8 Public events and clustering

4.8.1 Participation in public events and conferences

ENERGIZE+ will be presented in at least 10 national or international conferences, strategic workshops, seminars, fairs, or workshops relevant to industrial energy cooperatives. The aim is to share project outcomes, enlarge the dissemination reach of the project and promote the growth of the community in the ENERGIZE digital hub.

In particular, it is expected to present the project in two conferences per pilot country (Austria, Italy, Czech Republic, Catalonia) and two additional events in other EU regions. However, this planning will be adapted following the needs and requirements of the project development.

An initial set of conferences will be planned before M12.

4.8.2 Clustering with sister projects

Networking with other LIFE projects is also essential for increasing the reach and visibility of the project. ENERGIZE will promote clustering with at least 6 other relevant projects, to leverage synergies and foster cooperation. An initial selection of sister projects will be identified before M12.

4.8.3 Final ENERGIZE International Workshop

Towards the end of the project, ENERGIZE will organize an international workshop to present the final project results and showcase case studies, methodologies, guidelines, best practices, and business models.

To maximize impact, this event could be planned to coincide with a synergistic conference or exhibition for high impact, such as the European Sustainable Energy Week (EUSEW), the World Sustainable Energy Days (WSED), or any other similar event. Expected audience: 50 attendees.

4.9 Final publishable report

ENERGIZE will prepare a final publishable report presenting the key results, main lessons learnt, and recommendations for the future. The final publication should be professionally designed, attractive and tailored to the target group. The content and final draft of the publishable report must be discussed with CINEA before publication.

5 Monitoring

5.1 What to monitor

It is essential to understand the audience that has been reached by the project, both in quantitative and qualitative parameters. The reactions generated by the project and the level of satisfaction of the audience are crucial to better focus the following communication actions.

Monitoring activities will follow next scheme:

Figure 5-1 – Principles of monitoring and evaluation

5.2 Communication and dissemination KPIs

Next tables include the means of evaluation of the different communication and dissemination activities. The related KPIs are the objectives at the end of the project.

Table 5-1 – Communication and dissemination activities KPIs

COMMUNICATION AREA	KPIs	M36
PROJECT WEBSITE	Number of unique visitors Number of page views	2000+ 7500+
SOCIAL MEDIA	Number of followers Average publications per month	+50/quarter 15
VIDEOS	Number of short videos Number of views / reach of short videos Number of long videos Number of views / reach of long videos	10 200+ 2 400+
NEWSLETTER	Number of publications	6

	Number of reach / impressions / interactions	200+
PRESS RELEASES	Number of publications	6
AWARENESS RAISING CAMPAIGNS	Number of awareness raising campaigns	3
	Number of reach / impressions / interactions	3000+
CONFERENCES & EVENTS	Number of participated events	10
	Number of events organised by the project	1
	Number of attendants in organised events	50
SITE VISITS	Number of site visits	3
	Number of attendees	60+
CLUSTERING	Number of similar projects approached	6
ENERGIZE DIGITAL HUB	Number of registered users	200+
ENERGIZE NETWORK	Number of registered professional members to the project subscription list	200+

6 Dissemination of results & open access

6.1 Obligation to disseminate results

Dissemination (Grant Agreement – article 17) is a separate obligation. In that sense, each beneficiary must “disseminate” its results as soon as possible by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means, unless it goes against their legitimate interests. This does not change the obligation to protect results, confidentiality obligations, security obligations, or the obligation to protect personal data.

6.2 Information on EU funding – Obligation and right to use the LIFE emblem

Any communication activities (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant **must include**:

- a) The LIFE Programme flag. High resolution emblems can be found here:
https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/programmes/life/communication-and-gdpr-rules_en
- b) The following statement:
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6.3 Disclaimer excluding EU responsibility

Whenever using the funding logo (LIFE programme flag, EU logo, etc), this disclaimer will be used:

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7 Specific communication actions during 1st year

Table 7-1 – Communication and dissemination activities during 1st year of the project

ACTION	DEADLINE
Visual identity and project brand	M3
First operative version of the ENERGIZE landing webpage	M4
Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Plan	M5
Project flyer	M6
Project roll up	M6
Initial set of communication and dissemination material	M6
1 st ENERGIZE newsletter	M6
Identification of sister projects for clustering	M8
1 st ENERGIZE press release	M10
Production of ENERGIZE constitutional video	M10

More information: www.energizcommunity.eu

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